

ASCORBIC ACID OXIDASE FROM THE WHITE GOURD (*BENINCASACRIAPRA*).

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The preparation of an ascorbic acid oxidising enzyme from cabbage was described by Szent-Györgyi (*Science*, 1930, 72, 125; *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1931, 90, 385). Tauber, Kleiner and Mishkind (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1935, 110, 211) prepared an enzyme from Hubbard squash also capable of oxidising ascorbic acid reversibly and studied the properties of their preparation in some detail. Srinivasan (*Biochem. J.*, 1936, 30, 2077) prepared the same enzyme from the Indian drumstick. The distribution of the enzyme in plant and animal tissues was investigated by Chakraborty and Guha (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1937, 25, 839), who found the animal tissues to be practically devoid of the oxidase and observed that the cucumber and the white gourd (Bengali, *chalkumro*) were the richest sources among the plant materials investigated. An enzyme preparation from cucumber was obtained by Chakraborty (*private communication*) and has been described by Johnson and Zilva (*Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 438).

The present work was undertaken in order to obtain an ascorbic acid oxidase preparation from the white gourd (*Benincasacriapra*) and also to obtain information about its properties, the conditions of its activity and its specificity.

Fuller information about the properties of the ascorbic acid oxidase has become necessary particularly because it has been recommended as a reagent for the estimation of ascorbic acid (Tauber *et al*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1935, 110, 559) and its use has also been found to lead to more specific results in the estimations carried out in this laboratory which will be published later.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Enzyme.—The method followed was approximately that of Tauber (*et al loc. cit*). White gourd was minced in a hand mincer. 200 G. of minced plant tissue were shaken for 5 minutes with 600 c.c. of 30% alcohol and filtered. The p_n of the alcoholic filtrate was 5.0. To the alcoholic extract an equal volume of acetone was added and the precipitate quickly removed. It was dissolved in 80 c. c. of distilled

water and again precipitated with an equal volume of acetone. The enzyme was purified by repeating the process two or three times and then dried in a vacuum desiccator. It was light grey in colour.

On repeated purification the enzyme preparation becomes much lighter in colour. It appears to be fairly stable if stored in a vacuum desiccator at room temperature (26-30°). It takes some time to go into aqueous solution and for use the aqueous solution is centrifuged clear from a small residue. The aqueous solution lasts about a week if preserved with a drop or two of toluene in a stoppered vessel in a refrigerator. For the following experiments the solid enzyme preparation obtained from 200 g. of white gourd was dissolved in 80 c.c. of water.

A. Activity of the Enzyme at different p_H .

The activity of the enzyme was determined by the amount of ascorbic acid oxidised by the enzyme solution using 0.5 mg. of ascorbic acid as the substrate at 40° for 5 minutes at different p_H . After the period of incubation the enzyme activity was stopped by the addition of 1 c.c. of 2% sulphuric acid and titration was carried out with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol according to the method previously described (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 30).

TABLE IA.

Citrate phosphate buffer (McIlvaine)

The mixture consisted of citrate phosphate buffer (1 c.c.), enzyme solution (2 c.c.) and ascorbic acid (1 c.c., 0.5 mg).

p_H .	Amount of ascorbic acid oxidised.	Percentage of oxidation.
4.0	0.08 mg.	16%
4.4	0.10	20
5.2	0.20	40
5.4	0.20	40
5.6	0.22	44
6.2	0.20	40
6.8	0.16	32
7.2	0.10	20

TABLE I.

M- Acetate buffer.

The mixture consisted of *M*-acetate buffer (1 c.c.), enzyme solution (2 c.c.) and ascorbic acid solution (1 c.c., 0.5 mg.).

p_{H} .	Amount of ascorbic acid oxidised.	Percentage of oxidation.
4.5	0.20 mg.	40%
5.0	0.31	62
5.6	0.28	56

These experiments indicate that in citrate-phosphate buffer the optimum p_{H} is 5.6, whereas in *M*-acetate buffer it is about p_{H} 5.0.

B. Time of Complete Oxidation.

The mixture consisted of ascorbic acid solution (1 c.c.) containing 0.5 mg. of ascorbic acid, enzyme solution (2 c.c.) and *M*.acetate buffer (1 c.c.) incubated at 40°.

TABLE II.

Time.	Amount of ascorbic acid remaining unoxidised.	Percentage of oxidation.
5 min.	0.25 mg.	50%
10	0.20	60
15	0.12	72
30	0.00	100
45	0.00	100
60	0.00	100

Under these conditions of experiment, therefore, it would seem half an hour's incubation would be sufficient for the complete oxidation of 0.5 mg. of ascorbic acid.

C. Keeping the time and enzyme concentration constant, the relationship between the amount of oxidation and the concentration of the substrate was sought to be obtained.

The mixture consisted of *M*-acetate buffer (1 c.c.), enzyme solution (1 c.c.) and ascorbic acid solution of different concentrations. This was incubated at 40° for 5 minutes.

TABLE III.

Amount of ascorbic acid added.	Amount of ascorbic acid oxidised.
0.5 mg.	0.20 mg.
0.25	0.21
0.20	0.17
0.15	0.13
0.10	0.10

These results show that in the system, which we are using, with the given amount of enzyme maximum oxidation occurs when 0.25 mg. of ascorbic acid is present in 1 c. c. of solution. This information was necessary in connection with certain work on the estimation of ascorbic acid which is in progress in this laboratory (Sen-Gupta and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 95).

D. Specificity.—It was observed that the enzyme preparation was unable to oxidise glutathione, cysteine, hydroquinone and sodium thiosulphate. It must, therefore, be considered fairly specific. It should, however, be stated in this connection that its specificity may not be entirely strict, as recent investigations (Zilva, *Biochem. J.*, 1936, **30**, 1215) indicate that the ascorbic acid oxidase preparation from cucumber can also oxidise in varying degrees substances structurally closely related to ascorbic acid.

E. Inhibitors.—Potassium cyanide in concentration of $M/1000$ completely inhibits the action of the enzyme in a mixture of the type used in sections A and B. Sodium fluoride ($M/10$) seems to have a very slight inhibiting action on the enzyme preparation.

S U M M A R Y.

A preparation of ascorbic acid oxidase has been obtained from the white gourd (*Benincasacriapra*). Its properties, conditions of activity, specificity and the effect of certain reagents on its action are described.

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